

APPLICATION OF EMERGING ICT MEANS IN PRIMARY ESL CLASSES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract:

In a modern school, the learning process is well equipped. This includes an interactive whiteboard and the ability to access the Internet. All this makes the learning process more vibrant and attractive for schoolchildren. In our work, information technology acts as a means of implementing the principle of individualization. Informatization is taking place in the field of education and it could not but affect language education. The purpose of this article is to identify the possibilities of computer technology for the successful implementation of the principle of individualization.

Key words: computer training course, computer training system, computer textbook, teaching aids, controlling computer aids, training aids, didactic opportunities.

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At this time, the personality-oriented paradigm prevails in school. Speaking about the student-centered approach, it should be said that there is also a technology for student-centered learning. With this type of training, the dominant goal of education is the development of the personality as a whole, his individuality. The new vision of personal orientation is that the selection of content and the construction of the educational process are not so much aimed "at the individual, but rather come from the individual" - from his experience, requests, inclinations, abilities, needs for self-realization. Thus, the student is the subject of the process training [1].

However, there is a problem. A teacher at school works with a class of 25-30 people, rather than with one student. The teacher does not have the opportunity to choose the tools that are suitable for this student. This takes a lot of time and money. Information technologies have great potential.

In recent years, quite a lot of studies have appeared in which the authors described methods of teaching a foreign language based on information technology. P.V. worked on this. Sysoev, D.M. Gritskov, E.I. Passov, V.P. Kuzovlev, A.V. Zubov, G.K. Selevko, L.M. Fedorova and others. At the present stage, new requirements are imposed on the professional competence of teachers and teachers of a foreign language - having competence in the use of information technology, in teaching a foreign language and culture. However, an analysis of the experience of using information technologies in the educational process shows that for many teachers, the use of new computer technologies often comes down to the transfer of traditional classroom forms of work to teaching a foreign language through computer programs. At the same time, the colossal didactic potential of modern information and computer technologies is ignored, taking into account which would

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significantly enrich the linguistic and cultural practice of students, as well as develop their skills in independent learning activities [2].

Computer technologies nowadays are used in all spheres of human life, be it work, leisure or study. Information technology entered the learning process very quickly. They can be used in the process of explaining a new topic, when testing knowledge, to consolidate skills, and much more. Computer teaching technologies are the processes of preparing and transmitting information to the learner, the means of which is the computer.

Taking into account the goals and objectives of teaching foreign languages at a university among specialized computer teaching aids, Zubov A.V. allocates funds for training:

- phonetics;
- grammar;
- vocabulary;
- reading. [3]

Thus, computer teaching technologies have their own varieties: computer training course, computer training system, computer textbook, teaching aids, controlling computer aids, training aids, combined computer training aids, auxiliary computer training aids. This allows you to implement tasks of various types of lessons and achieve learning goals [4].

By constantly working with information technologies and their various types, didactic opportunities in teaching a foreign language are realized. The technology of electronic presentation of information and, what is especially important, the organization of search and access to this information allows in itself to effectively solve some particular didactic problems in teaching foreign languages. To learn a foreign language, you need to have a huge amount of information, which is also true when learning your native language.

Polat E.S. notes that the principle of visibility is especially effectively implemented in the conditions of a computerized educational process [5]. In the computer form of teaching, the didactic functions of clarity are expanded, since in addition to the traditional functions of semantization, presentation and systematization of language material, the creation of communicative situations and a psychological atmosphere, the computer allows, within the framework of one teaching tool, to implement almost all types of verbal and non-verbal clarity through the use of:

- Static visual aids (texts, photographs, drawings, diagrams, graphs, tables);
- Dynamic visual aids (animation, video track);
- Auditory aids (musical, noise and text accompaniment);
- Their combinations (sounding the text presented on the display, video). [6].

All these functions can be performed by an interactive whiteboard.

An interactive whiteboard is a high-tech device that ensures active student interaction with educational material. But to implement this active interaction, the educational material must be specially prepared. Software for interactive whiteboards is focused on teacher creativity. For example, the “Notebook” editor for the “Smart” interactive whiteboard has proven to be so effective that teachers use it to develop interactive learning tasks for use in classes equipped with computers, but without an interactive whiteboard [7]. The interactive whiteboard, which just a few years ago was perceived as a “magical” and rare phenomenon for high school, has now firmly gained a leading position among educational electronic devices. If we compare an interactive whiteboard with a personal computer, from the monitor of which digital materials can also be displayed on the screen, then a “smart board” can create conditions for collective work. Many authors note the special principle of visibility implemented by the interactive whiteboard, “both in relation to an individual student and to a whole group of students” [8].

Let's consider the principle of individualization, which in the computerized educational process in foreign languages is ensured by the following factors [9]:

An individual way of managing educational activities (the use of versions of computer programs of varying degrees of complexity based on testing the initial level of knowledge of students with the possibility of moving to simpler options for working with the program depending on the success of the results);

The ability to choose an individual pace of work (varying the speed of presentation of educational information on the display and the pace of interactive interaction between the student and the computer);

The ability to have access to the learning environment from your workplace at any time convenient for you [10];

Providing an individual set of learning support tools (reference materials, tips and keys);

Adaptation of the form of presentation of educational material to the individual characteristics of the perception of information by a specific user;

The opportunity for the student to train until he gets a result, which is achieved through the presence of a large number of exercises and the transfer of control means to the student. [9]

It is not by chance that didactics put forward the principle of individualization. Methodists also consider the principle of an individual approach necessary. G.V.Rogova writes: "One of the most important problems of educational technology is the search for ways to make greater use of the individual capabilities of students, both in conditions of collective work in the classroom and independent work outside of class time" [11,37]. Communicative learning presupposes, first of all, the so-called personal individualization. "By ignoring personal individualization," writes V.P. Kuzovlev, "we do not use the richest internal reserves of the individual." [8]

The process of organizing the education of schoolchildren using ICT allows you to individualize the learning process due to the presence of multi-level tasks, through immersion and assimilation of educational material at an individual pace, independently, using convenient ways of perceiving information, which evokes positive emotions in students and forms positive learning motives;

to liberate students when answering questions, because the computer allows you to record results (including without grading), and responds correctly to errors; independently analyze and correct mistakes made, adjust your activities thanks to the presence of feedback, as a result of which self-control skills are improved;

carry out independent educational and research activities (modelling, project method, development of presentations, publications, etc.), thereby developing creative activity in schoolchildren [1].

As mentioned above, the individualization of the learning process is carried out thanks to the powerful potential of computer tools and technologies.

To keep up with the times, the teacher must master the basics of information technology, have an understanding of the currently most common Windows operating system, be able to work in common computer programs, in particular Word, Excel, PowerPoint and a number of other specialized programs related to the subject. activities of the teacher, use the Internet, and also be able to use the knowledge of computers students acquired in information technology lessons. [3]

We conducted a theoretical study on this topic. We found out that individuality consists of 3 types: subjective, personal and individual. In their work, the teacher should

take into account all types of individualization [11]. The MHC, developed by V.P. Kuzovlev, is intended for this purpose. It is a table in which the surnames of students are vertically lined up, and individuality definitions are lined up horizontally. It may seem like a hassle to create an MHC, but experienced teachers can complete 40% of the table without taking tests. The very creation of the MHC pays off with the high motivation of students in their studies. And this is the most important thing in any activity.

Information technologies have become firmly entrenched in the education process in the last decade. And although they require processing and preparation for each class, they greatly facilitate the professional activity of the teacher. Information technologies help to implement all didactic principles, including the principle of individualization.

Today, many practicing teachers use computer technologies in their professional activities. In the next chapter we will get acquainted with the experience of practicing teachers.

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